

1 Efficient and sustainable recovery of lipids from sewage sludge using ethyl esters of volatile fatty acids
2 as sustainable extracting solvent

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24 ABSTRACT

25 This work focuses on the recovery of resources from urban sewage sludge. Sewage sludge is
26 generated by water treatment plants and contains a significant amount of lipids that can be used in a
27 number of applications in fine chemistry. This study reports the extraction of lipids from sewage sludge
28 using ethyl esters of volatile fatty acids as solvents. A thermodynamic study was first performed using
29 synthetic primary sludge in order to identify the best operating conditions to apply on real samples of
30 urban primary sludge. Ethyl butyrate showed the best separation performance. It was capable of
31 efficiently recovering the lipid component from primary sewage sludge, which typically resulted in 13-
32 23 % of total solids. Highly pure calcium soaps can be extracted in high amounts (yield up to 93 %),
33 while the exhausted residual aqueous phase resulted as not significantly contaminated by the solvent
34 and could be anaerobically digested easily. Finally, calcium soaps can be directly used as biolubricant
35 or efficiently converted into biodiesel using aluminum chloride hexahydrate as a catalyst (yield 85%).

36
37 **Keywords:** calcium soaps, sewage sludge, green extraction, biodiesel, biolubricants
38

39 1. INTRODUCTION

40 In Europe wastewater treatment processes produce around 10 million tonnes of sludge per year. This
41 figure will increase up to 13 million tonnes when the Wastewater Directive (91/271/EEC) is applied by
42 2020. Managing this waste in an economically, environmentally and socially acceptable way represents
43 one of the major issues which modern society needs to face today [1].

44 One promising and alternative way to manage sewage sludge is to save the chemical potential of
45 organic components through processes which isolate useful and valuable compounds [2]. Indeed, fresh
46 sludge is composed of organic components, and as such, has the potential to act as a source for
47 different high added-value products [3,4]. For instance, sewage sludge has attracted even greater

48 attention as a potential source of lipids which can be converted into conventional biofuel (namely
49 biodiesel as defined by EN14214) [5-7].

50 Lipid content in sewage sludge is remarkably high (up to 15-25% of dry weight) [3,8]. The
51 extraction of these lipids could result in an economically viable method for producing biodiesel which
52 is competitive with fossil derivatives [9]. However, the main challenge is to achieve an efficient
53 extraction of the lipid component from wet sludge, in which water can constitute up to 90-95% of the
54 raw biomass [3]. In previous works [10], it was estimated that more than 50 % of biodiesel production
55 costs derived from sludge dewatering and drying processes, which made the whole operations very
56 expensive. As such, the choice of the extraction solvent for the recovery of lipids from wet sewage
57 sludge represents a fundamental step.

58 A number of options have already been investigated based on the use of conventional [11-16] or
59 non-conventional [17] solvents (i.e. organic solvents or ionic liquids, respectively), alone or in their
60 mixture. The use of polar solvents (e.g. methanol [11], methanol/chloroform [12]) allows a high
61 amount of extractable fraction to be obtained, but the resulting oils and grease were heavily
62 contaminated by unsaponifiable matter and other polar compounds not convertible into biodiesel
63 [12,18]. In addition, the use of chlorinated solvents produces a highly toxic waste. On the other hand,
64 non-polar solvents (e.g. hexane [14,15], toluene [16]) are more selective in the extraction of
65 saponifiable lipids and can be used directly on wet sludge without any preliminary treatment. In
66 particular, hexane [14,15] is typically used as a solvent for the extraction of lipids from various
67 biomasses, due to a series of advantages including immiscibility with water, high selectivity, low
68 boiling point and cost.

69 In any case, the use of organic solvents to recover lipids from sludge produces a considerable
70 environmental impact. Organic solvents contaminate the residual exhausted biomasses by inhibiting
71 successive direct biodegradation, so much so that they require further expensive downstream processes

72 to clean and remove such residues [19]. In addition, it has also long been known that acidification
73 during extraction processes, especially on primary sludge (which results in the most proficient urban
74 sludge), generally helps in achieving best performances in terms of yields of extraction [20]. This point
75 was strictly correlated to the chemical nature of lipids present in primary sludge, mainly made up of
76 calcium soaps (>70%) [14]. Acidification, typically operated through the use of mineral acids,
77 promoted the conversion of soaps into FFAs, which are more soluble in the organic phase than the
78 abovementioned soaps [14]. On the other hand, such an addition of mineral acids during extraction
79 resulted in the production of an exhausted sewage sludge which is even more difficult to manage [20].
80 Indeed, along with contamination by organic solvents, a huge amount of the anionic counter-ion of the
81 mineral acid used during acid-extraction would be evaluated.

82 Considering that the separation of lipids from primary sludge without using organic solvents and
83 acids is not practicable, as in the case of sewage scum [21], an alternative approach might consist in
84 adopting different organic solvents, possibly with a lower environmental impact and without using
85 mineral acids. In this sense, the ethyl ester of volatile fatty acids (EEVFA) could represent a valuable
86 alternative. EEVFA are naturally occurring compounds, representing one of the main constituents of
87 fruits flavors [22]. They can be considered as bioderivable solvents, since they are industrially
88 obtainable through direct esterification of ethanol and VFA [23], which can be produced during the
89 fermentation of sugars of different kinds as well as food waste [24], agricultural residues [25] and even
90 from sewage sludge [26].

91 This study reports the use of EEVFA to extract lipids from sewage sludge without using any mineral
92 acids, with the aim of recovering the lipid fraction in its actual form. A preliminary study was initially
93 conducted on simulated sewage sludge, using calcium soaps as the model compound, in order to
94 identify the best operative conditions for recovering these lipids. Extraction phase diagrams were
95 experimentally determined using three specific EEVFA (ethyl acetate, ethyl propionate and ethyl

96 butyrate) and hexane, which was used as basis line for the analysis of the extraction process. These
97 phase diagrams were modelled with an artificial neural network (ANN) by including the experimental
98 recovery of lipids from real primary sludge. The best extraction conditions for the recovery of lipids
99 were identified and positively tested on real samples of sewage sludge. Calcium soaps of long chain
100 fatty acids were the main compounds extracted, isolated and converted into biodiesel. Finally, a
101 discussion on the possible direct applications of these lipids for fine purposes was also developed.

102

103 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

104 **2.1. Reagents and instruments**

105 All chemical reagents used in this work were of analytical grade and were used directly without further
106 purification or treatment. Methanol (CH_3OH , 99%), hexane (C_6H_{14} , 99%), ethyl acetate
107 ($\text{CH}_3\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$, $\geq 99.8\%$), ethyl propionate ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$, $\geq 99.5\%$), ethyl butyrate ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$,
108 $\geq 99.5\%$), potassium hydroxide (KOH, 85%), calcium chloride ($\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $>98\%$), toluene
109 ($\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $>99\%$) and methyl heptadecanoate ($\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_2$, $\geq 99\%$) were all purchased from Sigma-
110 Aldrich. Diethyl ether ($(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{O}$, 99%), nitric acid (HNO_3 , 65%), sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4 , 96%),
111 hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2 , 15%) and hydrochloric acid (HCl, 37%) were obtained as pure grade
112 reagents from Carlo Erba and J.T. Baker. Palm oil (food grade), cellulose (chromatography grade,
113 Sigma-Aldrich), and protein (casein $>80\text{-}90\%$, food grade) were purchased from Mystic Moment Ltd,
114 Carlo Erba and Isopure, respectively.

115 Gas chromatography–mass spectroscopy (GC–MS) for qualitative analysis were carried out using a
116 Perkin Elmer Clarus 500 gas-chromatograph interfaced with a Clarus 500 spectrometer. Quantitative
117 determinations were performed using a Thermo Scientific Trace 1300 gas chromatograph equipped
118 with a TG-5SILMS column (30 m, 0.25 mm, 0.25 μm). The temperature of the injector and the detector

119 were set at 523 and 573 K, respectively. The furnace operated with a temperature ramp of 10 K/min
120 starting at 313 K (which was kept constant for 2 min) and increased to the final temperature of 553 K.
121 This final temperature was kept constant for 10 min and a helium flow of 2.5 mL/min was used.

122 FTIR spectra were recorded using a Nicolet iS10 spectrometer (Thermo Scientific). The spectra
123 were recorded at room temperature using the Smart iTR accessory for ATR sampling with the ZnSe
124 crystal. Each sample was scanned 32 times over a wavenumber range of 4000 to 650 cm^{-1} with a
125 spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . X-ray diffraction analysis were conducted using an Empyrean (Malvern-
126 PANalytical) diffractometer. For X-ray diffraction analysis, the sample was mounted in a zero-
127 background silicon holder and data collection was performed at room temperature at the following
128 conditions: scan range from 1 to 50 $^{\circ}$ (2θ), step size of 0.02626 $^{\circ}$ and 145 s of time per step. X-ray
129 beam was collimated using fixed divergence and anti-scatter slits of 0.03125 $^{\circ}$ and 0.125 $^{\circ}$ and
130 diffracted beam slit of 7.5 mm. The detector employed for the analysis was a PIXcel1D-Medipix3 and
131 the geometry used in the measurement was the Bragg-Brentano. The software HighScore Plus and the
132 PDF2 database were used to interpret the diffraction pattern.

133 Calcium analysis was performed on mineralized samples using a Thermo Scientific iCE3000 AA
134 Spectrometer. 0.02-0.05 g of sample was suspended in 10 mL of HNO_3 , 5 mL of H_2O_2 and heated for 2
135 h at 503 K using a heat plate. The mineralized samples were then dissolved into Milli-Q water and
136 analyzed.

137

138 **2.2. Primary sludge**

139 Real samples of primary sludge were collected from the municipal wastewater treatment plant located
140 in the city of Aguascalientes, Mexico. This treatment plant has a capacity of 2000 L/s raw wastewater.
141 The sludge was dehydrated and the amounts of saponifiable lipids, total solids (TS) and ash were
142 determined using the procedures reported by di Bitonto et al. [21] Samples were immediately

143 processed, through dewatering (centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 5 minutes or filtration) up to a TS
144 content of 8-12% and immediately used to avoid a long period of storage (at 277 K).

145

146 **2.3. Fatty Acid profile and determination of Average Molecular Weight (AMW)**

147 In a glass Pyrex reactor of 5 mL, 40 mg grease sample was weighed and suspended with 2 mL of
148 solution toluene, methanol and concentrated H₂SO₄ (2:2:0.01 v/v/v). The reactor was closed and placed
149 into an ultrasonic bath at 343 K for 5 h. Following this, 1 mL 1000 ppm methyl heptadecanoate
150 solution was added as internal standard. Average Molecular Weight (*AMW*) was determined gas-
151 chromatographically (1 μL) according to the following equation (Eq. 1):

$$AMW = \frac{\sum A_i MW_i}{\sum A_i} \quad (1)$$

152 where *A_i* and *MW_i* are the area and molecular weight of each single FFA determined experimentally.

153

154 **2.4. Fundamental thermodynamic study of the lipid extraction using EEVFA**

155 **2.4.1. Synthesis of calcium soaps of palm oil**

156 Considering that lipids in primary sewage sludge are mainly based on palmitic and stearic calcium
157 soaps [14], palm oil was chosen as starting material for preparing synthetic calcium soaps to be used for
158 the thermodynamic study of extraction. In a round bottom-flask of 250 mL equipped with a reflux
159 condenser, 10.05 g palm oil was weighed, and 3.00 g KOH solubilized in 100 mL ethanol was added .
160 Saponification of palm oil was carried out under reflux for 2 h using a thermostatic bath. At the end of
161 the process, the system was allowed to cool to room temperature (297 K) and a magnetic stirrer was
162 introduced. 4.1 g CaCl₂·H₂O dissolved in 10 mL of water was then added dropwise under agitation
163 (300 rpm). The resulting suspension was kept at 277 K for at least 24 h in order to obtain

164 sedimentation. Finally, solids obtained were filtered (Whatman no. 40 paper), washed with deionized
165 water (3 L) and dried for 24 h at 373 K. The yield of saponification reactions for the synthesis of the
166 calcium soaps ranged from 85 to 92 %.

167

168 **2.4.2. Experimental set-up for the phase-equilibrium study**

169 Phase equilibrium data for the lipid extraction were measured using a synthetic mixture composed of
170 50 mL of deionized water, 1 g of cellulose, 2 g of protein and 2 g of calcium soaps. Hexane, ethyl
171 acetate, ethyl propionate and ethyl butyrate were the solvents employed in the extraction studies of
172 calcium soaps. Phase diagrams were obtained by varying the amount of the solvent from 4 to 44.5 g
173 with the extraction data that were recorded at 297 K and pH of 6.4 ± 0.1 . The solvent and aqueous
174 solution containing the calcium soaps, cellulose and protein were mixed at 297 K for 1 h under constant
175 stirring of 250 rpm. The organic and aqueous phases were separated (after 3 h of settling) and the
176 masses of both phases were measured gravimetrically. The solvent was evaporated and quantified by
177 difference. All the experiments were performed in duplicate and the average value was employed for
178 data analysis. The mass of all components of the thermodynamic system was determined with an
179 accuracy of ± 0.001 g. Finally, a 100 mg sample of dehydrated solids derived from the extraction was
180 grounded and reacted with 4 mL of a methanolic solution of 2 g/L of methyl heptadecanoate (used as
181 internal standard) at 373 K for 2 h in presence of HCl conc. (30 mg). The content of the methyl esters
182 of fatty acids (FAMES) in the final solution was analyzed with gas chromatography following the
183 procedure reported by di Bitonto et al. [21]

184

185 **2.4.3. Experimental phase diagrams for the extraction of calcium soaps**

186 Tie-lines of the extraction phase diagrams were calculated through the mass balances and FAMES
187 quantifications. A ternary system was considered for the data analysis, which implied the mass

188 composition (m_i , g) of the calcium soaps J , solvent S and a pseudo-component Ps formed by the
 189 aqueous solution containing the protein and cellulose. This approach allowed to visualize and analyze
 190 the extraction thermodynamic data in a ternary phase diagram. The mass compositions of J , S and Ps
 191 were calculated using the following equations (Eqs. 2-4):

$$J = S_{des} * \%FAMES_{des} / \%FAMES \quad (2)$$

$$S = M_{tot} - M_{ex} \quad (3)$$

$$Ps = M_{ex} + [M_{sec} - (S_{des} * (\%FAMES_{des} / \%FAMES))] \quad (4)$$

192 where S_{des} is the mass of dehydrated solids (expressed in g), M_{tot} is the mass of a single phase
 193 (expressed in g), M_{ex} and M_{sec} are the masses of solvents removed after the extraction and relevant
 194 evaporation of water (both given in g), $\%FAMES_{des}$ and $\%FAMES$ are the mass percentages of FAMES
 195 quantified in the dehydrated solids and raw calcium soaps, respectively. The corresponding mass
 196 fractions w_{ij} were obtained for each tie-line of the extraction data (Eq. 5):

$$w_{ij} = m_{ij} / \sum_{k=1}^3 m_{kj} \quad (5)$$

197 where m_{ij} is the mass (g) of component i at phase j . Finally, m_{kj} is the mass (g) of all components at
 198 phase j .

199 The thermodynamic consistency of experimental extraction data was also assessed, according to the
 200 literature [27-29]: the tie-lines obtained for ternary diagrams should show a linear trend if the mass
 201 fractions w_{ij} are used as composition variables. Therefore, the Hand [27] and Othmer-Tobias [28]
 202 models were used to verify the thermodynamic consistency of extraction data for the calcium soaps
 203 recovery.

204 These models are defined as (Eqs. 6-7):

$$\ln(\beta) = A + B \ln(\alpha) \quad (6)$$

$$\ln (\Phi)= A' + B' \ln (\Omega) \quad (7)$$

205 The next nomenclature was utilized for the linear regressions (Eqs. 8-11):

$$\Phi = \ln \left(w_{J,A} / w_{Ps,A} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$\Omega = \ln \left(w_{J,O} / w_{S,O} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$\beta = \ln \left(1 - w_{S,O} / w_{S,O} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$\alpha = \ln \left(1 - w_{Ps,A} / w_{Ps,A} \right) \quad (11)$$

206

207 where β and α are the straight line in the graphic to Othmer-Tobias model, Φ and Ω the straight line in
 208 the graphic to Hand model, formed from the mass fractions w_{ij} . A , B , A' and B' are parameters of the
 209 model, $w_{Ps,A}$ and $w_{J,A}$ are the mass fractions of the pseudo-component Ps and calcium soaps J in the
 210 aqueous phase, while $w_{J,O}$ and $w_{S,O}$ are the mass fractions of the calcium soaps J and the solvent S in
 211 the organic phase, respectively. A linear regression was performed and the determination coefficient R^2
 212 was used as a metric of the degree of thermodynamic consistency of experimental data [26-29].

213 After performing the thermodynamic data consistency, the best conditions for the lipid recovery were
 214 identified for each solvent. The recovery of calcium soaps (R_J , %) was calculated by using Eq. 12:

$$R_j, \% = m_{J,O} / m_{J,F} * 100 \quad (12)$$

215 where $m_{J,O}$ is the mass of calcium soaps in the organic phase (i.e., solvent) and $m_{J,F}$ is the mass of
 216 calcium soaps in the feed used to obtain the corresponding tie-line in the extraction phase diagram,
 217 respectively.

218 The solute partition coefficient (D) and solvent selectivity (S) [30] were also employed to
 219 characterize the efficiency of calcium soap separation with EEVFA and hexane (Eqs. 13-14):

$$D = w_{J,O} / w_{J,A} \quad (13)$$

$$S = \left(w_{J,O} / w_{J,A} \right) / \left(w_{Ps,O} / w_{Ps,A} \right) \quad (14)$$

220 where $w_{J,O}$ and $w_{J,A}$ are the mass fractions of calcium soaps in the organic and aqueous phases, $w_{Ps,O}$
221 and $w_{Ps,A}$ are the mass fractions of the pseudocomponent in the organic and aqueous phases,
222 respectively.

223

224 2.4.4. Modelling with an ANN

225 The modeling of the extraction of calcium soap was performed with an ANN [31]. Figure 1
226 illustrates the model utilized to fit the extraction data. This model correlates some compositional
227 properties of the sludge, the amount and some physico-chemical properties of the solvents with the
228 respective recoverability of soaps from sludge. A feed-forward ANN with backpropagation modeled
229 the extraction diagrams by application of the following equations (Eqs. 15-16):

$$Y_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^{n_{i-1}} u_{ijk} V_{i-1,k} + \theta_{ij} \quad (15)$$

$$V_{ij} = g(Y_{ij}) \quad (16)$$

230 where Y_{ij} is the net input of the neuron j in the layer i , u_{ijk} is the connection weight, V_{ik} is the neuron
231 input, θ_{ij} is the neuron bias and $g(Y_{ij})$ corresponds to the tangent-sigmoidal activation function that is
232 utilized to calculate the neuron output V_{ij} given in the set of neuron inputs, respectively. The values of
233 parameters u_{ijk} and θ_{ij} for each neuron of this ANN model were determined via a training process with
234 the experimental extraction data. The input variables of ANN model were density and solubility in
235 water of the solvents (reported into Table 1), the concentration of saponifiable lipids and total solids in
236 the starting sludge, and the last input variable was the mass ratio between the solvent and the wet
237 sludge. The recovery of calcium soaps was taken as the output variable. Various models were
238 performed changing the number of neurons and hidden layers. The best option was a model of 2 hidden
239 layer with 10 neurons in each layer. ANN modeling of extraction data was carried out with Matlab®
240 software using the corresponding neural network toolbox. The training of ANN model was performed

241 with the Bayesian Regularization numerical method, where experimental extraction data were used for
242 training (50 % of which from experiments using simulated sludge and 50 % from real primary sludge).
243 Two different tests were carried out at the end: a first one on random data selected by Matlab®
244 program and a second one on extraction data on real samples of sewage sludge.

245

246 **2.5 Extraction studies in samples of sewage sludge from a wastewater treatment plant**

247 Hexane and ethyl butyrate were used as solvents. In each test, 55 g of the dewatered sludge were
248 used with the extraction experiments which were carried out according to the procedures described
249 above for the extraction phase diagrams (297 K, pH = 6.4, 1 atm), using different amounts of solvents.
250 While processing of these real samples, the extracted organic phase was recovered and centrifuged at
251 4000 rpm for 1 min or filtered. In this way, two lipid components can be quantified and distinguished:
252 namely soluble and insoluble lipids. Both lipids were isolated after evaporation of solvents as residue,
253 and they were weighted before being analyzed. Elemental analysis, FTIR, XRD and gas
254 chromatographic profile after derivatization were conducted.

255

256 **2.6. Chemical up-grade of insoluble lipid phase recovered from sewage sludge into biodiesel**

257 In a Falcon tube of 50 mL, 5 g of insoluble solid lipids were suspended in 5 g of methanol (weight
258 ratio lipids to MeOH = 1) and kept under agitation for 1 h at 298 K. Then, 1 g of formic acid was added
259 dropwise (weight ratio lipids to HCOOH = 5), by obtaining the conversion of calcium soaps into the
260 corresponding FFAs [32]. After 2 h of reaction, the methanol solution was recovered by filtration and
261 transferred into a glass reactor of 25 mL. Fatty acids were then converted into methyl esters, adopting
262 the optimized conditions of direct esterification described by Pastore et al. [33].

263 0.3 g of $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were solubilized in therein with the reaction that was carried out at 344 K for 4
264 h using a thermostatic bath. At the end of the process, a biphasic system was obtained consisting of: i) a
265 methanol layer in which the catalyst was mainly dissolved in and ii) a lower oily layer formed by
266 methyl esters of fatty acids. The fatty layer was recovered and residual methanol was evaporated (330
267 K, 30 mTorr). The residue (about 4.3 g) was analyzed as pure fatty acid methyl esters (purity >95%,
268 yield = 86%).

269

270 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

271 **3.1. Extraction phase diagrams for the recuperation of calcium soaps**

272 The theoretical thermodynamic study for the lipid extraction was carried out using a synthetic
273 sample whose composition emulated the nature of a dewatered primary sewage sludge obtained from a
274 real municipal wastewater treatment plant. Experimental thermodynamic studies were performed to
275 obtain the extraction phase diagrams and to identify the best operating conditions. Calcium soaps were
276 used as the model compound to represent the lipid phase present in sewage sludge samples. As
277 denoted, these soaps are the main components in the lipid fraction in this sludge [14]. In detail, lipids in
278 urban primary sludge are mainly calcium palmitates and stearates. For this reason, synthetic calcium
279 soaps used in the thermodynamic study were obtained from palm oil according to the procedure
280 reported in the previous Section. Figure 2 shows the FTIR spectrum, GC-FID profile of FFAs after
281 derivatization and X-ray diffraction pattern of the soaps utilized in the extraction studies. With respect
282 to FTIR results as reported in Figure 2a, the absorption bands at 1538 and 1574 cm^{-1} are associated to
283 the carboxylic salts, while bands at 2850 and 2918 cm^{-1} can be attributed to aliphatic chains of calcium
284 soaps [34]. Previous studies [14,35] reported the FTIR characterization of the lipids contained in sludge
285 samples obtained from a water treatment plant. These studies concluded that the lipid fraction of
286 sewage sludge was composed mainly of calcium soaps, which were identified with the absorption

287 bands at 1538 and 1576 cm^{-1} . On the other hand, the results of gas chromatography were used to
288 estimate a molecular weight of 572-578 g/mol for the calcium salts of fatty acids. Chemical
289 derivatization of calcium soaps allowed the organic component as methyl esters of fatty acids to be
290 defined, with respect to methyl heptadecanoate, which was used as an internal standard. The
291 distribution of the different fatty acids was also evaluated. Palmitic (C16:0) and oleic (C18:1) acids
292 were the main compounds present with a composition of 38-45% and 30-35%, respectively, as denoted
293 in Figure 2b. Willson et al. [36] have demonstrated that the lipids of the sewage sludge showed a high
294 content of palmitic (35-40%), stearic and oleic (15-25%) acids. Therefore, these results were consistent
295 with those obtained in the characterization of the calcium soaps that were utilized to perform the
296 thermodynamic extraction tests.

297 Results of X-ray diffraction of calcium soaps are reported in Figure 2c. The crystalline structure of
298 calcium stearate was identified and this result was consistent with that obtained by gas
299 chromatography, where the presence of the C18 chain was confirmed. The X-ray diffraction pattern of
300 calcium soap showed two regions of sharp and intense peaks; the first one was located between 2 and
301 10° (2θ) and the second around 20 and 30° (2θ), which confirmed its crystalline structure [38-40].
302 According to Vold and Hattiangdi [37], the peaks located at angles $\leq 10^\circ$ (2θ) are generated from the
303 diffraction of X-rays by planes of atoms whose separation is proportional to the length of the soap
304 molecule. Specifically, the peaks at small angles of the analyzed sample were located at 1.98 ($d = 46$
305 \AA), 3.87 (22 \AA), 5.89 (15 \AA), 7.83 (11 \AA) and 9.88 (9 \AA) $^\circ$ (2θ). The first four signals could be
306 attributed to (100), (200), (300) and (400) diffractions of the bilayer structures indicating that the
307 particles were in a lamellar crystalline state [37-39,41]. Note that Vold and Hattiangdi [37] stated that
308 the peaks located at 20.22 ($d = 4.38 \text{\AA}$), 21.14 (4.19 \AA), 21.96 (4.04 \AA) and 26.28 (3.38 \AA) $^\circ$ (2θ) could
309 be obtained from the diffraction of X-ray from planes of atoms separated by smaller distances and they
310 were thus referred to as short spacing.

311 Figure 3 displays the experimental ternary phase diagrams for the extraction of calcium soaps with
312 the four solvents where the tie-lines are given in mass fractions w . All phase diagrams can be classified
313 as Type I where they showed a two-phase region (i.e., aqueous phase and organic solvent phase).
314 However, the aqueous phase is difficult to appreciate since its equilibrium experimental data were close
315 to w_{ps} axis. The experimental extraction data indicated that the phase splitting region obtained with
316 hexane and ethyl butyrate was greater than those of ethyl acetate and ethyl propionate. This finding
317 implied that the immiscibility between the organic and aqueous phases that contained the calcium soaps
318 increased when these solvents were the extracting agents. The differences in the extraction phase
319 diagrams can be associated to the polarity and water solubility of tested solvents. In particular, the trend
320 of water solubility of the solvents was as follows: hexane < ethyl butyrate < ethyl propionate < ethyl
321 acetate. Therefore, the two-phase area increased with the hydrophobicity of the solvents. Overall,
322 hexane and ethyl butyrate showed the best separation performance to recover the calcium soaps from
323 tested experimental matrix.

324 Results of the thermodynamic consistency of the extraction phase diagrams are reported in Figure 4.
325 The determination coefficients (R^2) for Othmer-Tobias models [28] ranged from 0.81 to 0.96, while the
326 linear fittings with Hand equation [27] showed R^2 values of 0.82-0.98. The major uncertainties of
327 experimental data corresponded to the extraction studies performed with ethyl acetate, which had the
328 highest water solubility. However, these uncertainties were not significant and this phase diagram was
329 thermodynamically consistent. These results confirmed the mutual consistency and reliability of all
330 extraction experimental data obtained with EEVFA and hexane and validated their application for
331 process design and modeling.

332 The recovery of calcium soaps with EEVFA and hexane are given in Figure 5. The resulting values
333 ranged from 82 to 98 % using 4-44.5 g of tested solvents per 55 g of starting wet mixture. It was clear
334 that these recoveries followed the next tendency: hexane \cong ethyl butyrate > ethyl propionate > ethyl

335 acetate. In fact, the ethyl acetate was outperformed by other EEVFA and hexane. This ethyl ester
336 showed the worst tradeoff between the calcium soap recovery and the solvent used in separation.
337 Figure 5 indicated that the application of the ethyl acetate to separate the calcium soaps implied a
338 substantial increment in the solvent amount to obtain a similar extraction performance than those
339 reported for other EEVFA and hexane. Such an aspect could be interpreted as an effect of the
340 increasing solubility in water with the decreasing of the EEVFA. This context could imply major
341 operational costs of the extraction system for processing the lipids from the sewage sludge with ethyl
342 acetate due to the associated increment of the process equipment dimensions and the recuperation of
343 the solvent for its reuse and final disposal. On the simulated sludge, high recovery percentages (i.e.,
344 ~96 %) were reached to separate the calcium soaps with hexane and ethyl butyrate using the minimum
345 solvent amounts (i.e., 7.2 and 12.7 g, respectively). It is clear that higher mass amounts of ethyl
346 butyrate were needed to reach the hexane recoveries. However in terms of optimization, 12.7 g of ethyl
347 butyrate were already enough and suitable to recover high amounts (~96 %) of calcium soaps.

348 The calculated values of partition coefficients D ranged from 72 to 143, 40 to 45, 34 to 124 and 49
349 to 142 for hexane, ethyl acetate, ethyl propionate and ethyl butyrate, respectively; while solvent
350 selectivity S was in the order of 1164-11750, 80-1790, 315-526 and 794-2742, see Figure 6. Hexane
351 and ethyl butyrate showed the highest values of solvent selectivity and partition coefficients thus
352 confirming their better separation performance to extract the calcium soaps. A high value of D implies
353 the reduction of the solvent to be used in the separation process to obtain proficient results [30].
354 Therefore, hexane and ethyl butyrate were the best options to recover the calcium soaps from tested
355 thermodynamic matrix.

356

357 **3.2. ANN model for determining recoverability of lipids from real sewage sludge**

358 Preliminary results showed that the modeling of tested separation systems with traditional
359 thermodynamic equations was challenging. Therefore, an ANN was utilized to simulate extraction on
360 real primary sewage sludge. In fact, the composition of primary sewage sludge is much more complex
361 than that of the synthetic sludge used into the study reported above. Inorganic components (20 %) and
362 ligno-humic compounds (up to 30 %) can be find therein. In order to deal with this higher chemical
363 complexity and variability of real sludge, the ANN model was created using experimental
364 recoverability of soaps obtained from simulated (20 data) and real primary sludge (20 data). Figure 7
365 shows the results of extraction data modeling with ANN. Overall, it is clear that the proposed structure
366 of ANN was capable of predicting the final recoverability with a satisfactory level of confidence (R^2
367 value was higher than 0.97), by only needing two specific parameters related to the sludge: TS and the
368 initial saponifiable lipid content referred to TS. A selection of the experimental recoverability obtained
369 on real sludge is reported in Table 2. The best results (Entries 14, 15 and 16), with the highest
370 recoverability (up to 93.3%), were obtained when extractions were carried out using an unitary weight
371 ratio of ethyl butyrate to dewatered sludge. By reducing the amount of solvent, the recovery of soaps
372 from real sludge became less efficient compared to when carried out on simulated ones. This is due to
373 the more complex composition of sludge [3]. Indeed, the presence of a significant amount of humic-
374 like compounds might confer to the sewage sludge very different physico-chemical properties, which
375 lead to a reduction of the final recoverability, in any case very predictable by the application of the
376 ANN model.

377

378 **3.3. Recovery of lipids from sewage sludge samples**

379 The extracting performance of hexane and ethyl butyrate using the best operating conditions were
380 eventually tested on samples of dewatered primary sewage sludge. Primary sludge was up-taken
381 monthly and found to contain an amount of saponifiable lipids which ranged from 12.8 to 23 % of TS.

382 In accordance with previous experimental results on synthetic mixture, lipids were efficiently extracted
383 from dewatered primary sludge with recoveries higher than 90%, using both solvents, namely hexane
384 and ethyl butyrate. These were subsequently quantified and characterized, confirming the prevalent
385 presence of calcium fatty soaps. The organic phase obtained from the extraction appeared as a greenish
386 or yellowish solution, in which a white solid was finely suspended. Centrifugation (or filtration) can be
387 efficiently used to separate and distinguish insoluble lipids from the soluble parts. Both were quantified
388 by weighting the residues after the evaporation of solvents. The insoluble component was the most
389 consistent part: approximately 70-90% of total extracted lipids were solids, whereas the soluble
390 components accounted for the remaining 10-30%. Solids were then analyzed and found to contain a
391 significant amount of calcium in the range of 5-7%. FTIR spectra and XRD profile, reported in Figure
392 2, evidenced the presence of calcium soaps of fatty acids. In FTIR spectra, the absorption bands
393 centered at 1540 and 1576 cm^{-1} and typical of calcium soaps were detected [34]. While X-ray
394 diffraction pattern of calcium soap showed sharp and intense peaks located between 2 and 10 $^{\circ}$ (2θ) and
395 around 20 and 30 $^{\circ}$ (2θ), which confirmed the presence of the crystalline structure of calcium stearate
396 and palmitate [37-41].

397 The proficiency of the conversion of these insoluble lipids into biodiesel was therefore
398 experimentally tested according to a well-defined procedure [32]. This method consisted of a two-step
399 process: in the first step, soaps were converted into FFAs using formic acid, whereas in the second step,
400 FFAs were converted into FAMES through a direct esterification mediated by $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. In detail,
401 the insoluble components of lipids extracted from sludge were suspended in dry methanol (solid
402 lipids:MeOH 1:1 by weight). Formic acid was then added (solid lipid:HCOOH 5:1 by weight) and the
403 resulting suspension was kept at room temperature under stirring for 2 h [32]. Through filtration a
404 limpid uncolored solution was then separated from a greyish solid (analyzed as calcium formate), and
405 treated with $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ under optimized reactive conditions in order to carry out direct esterification

406 of FFAs [33]. Methanol and water were subsequently evaporated and the mixture of FAMES was
407 finally isolated (GC-FID yield over 85 %wt).

408

409 **3.4. Impact of the method and preliminary feasibility study**

410 The recovery of calcium soaps from sewage sludge may have a major positive economic impact.
411 Calcium stearate and palmitate are known to have good properties as solid lubricants [42] and are,
412 indeed already widely used in this field. Furthermore, the value of calcium soaps is around 1-2 Euro
413 per kg [43], and there are significant positive environmental advantages associated. Around 45 Mt of
414 lubricants are used worldwide annually [44]. In Europe alone, according to European Commission
415 resources, 5.7 Mt yr⁻¹ of lubricants are used and, a significant part is actually recovered and recycled:
416 only around 1.5 Mt year⁻¹ needs to be replaced and manufactured since lost, half of which (0.7 Mt) in
417 an uncontrolled way [45]. Under these conditions the replacement of fossil oils with bioderived (from
418 exhausted feedstocks) and biodegradable lubricants might significantly mitigate the environmental
419 impact due to this dispersion [46]. At the Aguascalientes wastewater treatment plant, sewage produced
420 by 800,000 People Equivalent is typically treated and around 20,000 t of dry solids per year of primary
421 sludge are produced. Indeed, around 60 g of dry primary sludge are normally recovered per person per
422 day [14]. According to experimental determinations, the content of calcium soaps into primary sludge
423 is between 12.8 and 23 % of TS. Under these constraints, 3,500 t per year of calcium soaps could be
424 potentially provided by the wastewater treatment plant in Aguascalientes.

425 The layout of the plant for the extraction of calcium soaps in this specific case needs to be
426 dimensioned for the processing of around 200,000 t per year of dewatered primary sludge (10 %wt of
427 TS). More specifically, 550 t of dewatered primary sludge per day should be processed, whereas the
428 respective optimized ethyl butyrate would require 150 t day⁻¹. Considering that the resultant exhausted
429 aqueous phase derived by the extraction was found only to be slightly contaminated (around 1-1.5

430 %wt, which represent the 2-3% of solvent adopted per cycle), 1,500 t of ethyl butyrate would need to
431 be dispersed and replaced with fresh solvent annually, if not properly recovered. However, ethyl
432 butyrate is a bioderivable and biodegradable solvent which can offer additional advantages, mainly in
433 terms of environmental impact, when compared to hexane. Indeed, differently from the aqueous
434 residues derived from hexane extraction [19], such a slight contamination does not represent a problem
435 in terms of inhibition of anaerobic treatment in the case of ethyl butyrate [47]. In the worst scenario,
436 where ethyl butyrate trapped in residual sludge is not recovered and directly sent to an anaerobic
437 digester, a significant profit would, in any case, be potentially generated. Depending on the
438 recoverability of soaps, which is typically between 60 and 90%, 2,100,000-3,150,000 Euro would be
439 obtained annually by selling the calcium soaps considering a price of 1 Euro/Kg. On the other hand,
440 the consumption of 1,500 tonnes of ethyl butyrate would count for 1,500,000 Euro per year. As a
441 consequence, profits would total between 600,000 and 1,650,000 Euro per year.

442 Capital costs of a simplified configuration of a lipid extraction plant were calculated using Aspen
443 plus® software. Plant configuration included two steel extractors (35 m³), 2 centrifuges (1 capable of
444 processing 58 m³/h and another of 29 m³) and a decanter of 140 m³, see Figure 8. It was assumed that
445 the extraction process would be located near (or within) the treatment plant to avoid the cost of sludge
446 transportation. Sludge volume entering the first centrifuge was defined as 1,375 m³ (wet sludge with 4
447 % wt of total solids). Note that a centrifuge with a capacity of 58 m³/h or 2 centrifuges with a capacity
448 of 29 m³/h can be utilized to process approximately 58 m³/h of a decanted primary sludge. The
449 modeling scenario considered that this dewatered sludge (23 m³/h) was introduced into a mixer with
450 7.11 m³/h of ethyl butyrate. Two 35 m³ mixers were considered in parallel with 1 h of stirring. It was
451 also necessary to introduce a decanter as a static separator with a capacity of 140 m³ for a retention
452 time of 4 h. Two decanter outputs (heavy and light phases) were obtained where the light phase entered
453 into a filtering system with a flow of approximately 7 m³/h. Note that the filtration process is important

454 because when the ethyl butyrate was saturated with calcium soaps, solids (i.e., calcium soaps) can be
455 suspended in the light phase and can be easily recovered with mechanical processes such as filtration.
456 Meanwhile, the heavy phase was subjected to a centrifugation process to recover the maximum amount
457 of solvent and lipids from the processed sludge. The simulator introduced inlets and equipment. The
458 database of costs included in Aspen Plus® estimated a value of capital costs (installation and
459 equipment costs) of 1,400,000 Euro, which would be recovered in few years considering the
460 abovementioned potential yearly profit.

461

462 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

463 In this study the use of ethyl esters of volatile fatty acids for the recovery of lipids from sewage
464 sludge was analyzed and compared. An artificial neural network can provide a reliable surrogate model
465 to predict the performance of extraction processes associated to the recovery of lipids from primary
466 sewage sludge. Theoretical thermodynamic studies confirmed that ethyl butyrate provides a valid
467 alternative and effective green solvent to extract calcium soaps, able to compete with the performance
468 of hexane. This green solvent showed the ability to recover large amounts of lipids from samples of
469 sewage sludge which could be used in several fields from fuels (biodiesel precursor) to fine chemicals
470 (biolubricants). The use of EEVFA for extracting lipids would become a further feasible process which
471 can be employed in the complex biorefinery of sewage sludge. Indeed, not only would EEVFA be
472 produced from urban sludge, but they could also be used *in situ* to recover new fine chemicals from the
473 same feedstock. In addition, they are easily hydrolysable in an aqueous environment, by regenerating
474 ethanol and VFAs, which are completely biodegradable. For all these reasons, the use of EEVFA as
475 extracting solvents would minimize the environmental impact when compared to the use of
476 conventional solvents.

477

478

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484

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615 4

7. APPENDAGE

7.1 Figures

Figure 1. Architecture of the artificial neural network model used for the prediction of phase diagrams of the extraction of calcium soaps with different solvents. (This figure is for a 2-column size)

Figure 2. FTIR spectrum, GC-FID profile of FFAs after derivatization and X-ray diffraction pattern of synthetic calcium soaps (a), b) and c)) and real sewage sludge (a'), b') and c')) respectively. (This figure is for a size of one column)

Figure 3. Experimental phase diagrams for the extraction of calcium soaps using hexane and EEVFA in emulated sludge. This ternary system included the calcium soaps J , solvent S and a pseudo-component Ps formed by the aqueous solution containing the protein and cellulose. (This figure is for a 2-column size)

Figure 4. Results of thermodynamic consistency of experimental calcium soaps extraction diagrams using Hand [27] and b) Othmer-Tobias [28] models in emulated sludge. (This figure is for a size of one column)

Figure 5. Recovery for the extraction of calcium soaps using ethyl esters of volatile fatty acids and hexane in emulated sludge. Experimental conditions: 297 K and 250 rpm during 1 h. (This figure is for a size of one column)

Figure 6. Solvent selectivity and partition coefficients for the extraction of calcium soaps using ethyl ester of volatile fatty acids and hexane in emulated sludge. (This figure is for a size of one column)

Figure 7. Results of the ANN modeling of phase extraction diagrams for the recovery of calcium soaps using ethyl esters of volatile fatty acids and hexane. Data a) and b) used for training and c) testing of ANN. (This figure is for a 2-column size)

Figure 8. Scheme of valorization of primary sludge to obtain calcium soaps. (This figure is for a 2-column size)

Figure 1. Architecture of the artificial neural network model used for the prediction of phase diagrams of the extraction of calcium soaps with different solvents.

Figure 2. FTIR spectrum, GC-FID profile of FFAs after derivatization and X-ray diffraction pattern of synthetic calcium soaps (a), b) and c)) and real sewage sludge (a'), b') and c')) respectively.

a) Hexane

b) Ethyl acetate

c) Ethyl propionate

d) Ethyl butyrate

Figure 3. Experimental phase diagrams for the extraction of calcium soaps using hexane and EEVFA in emulated sludge. This ternary system included the calcium soaps J , solvent S and a pseudo-component P_s formed by the aqueous solution containing the protein and cellulose.

a) Hand model

b) Othmer-Tobias model

Figure 4. Results of thermodynamic consistency of experimental calcium soaps extraction diagrams using a) Hand [27] and b) Othmer-Tobias [28] models in emulated sludge.

Figure 5. Recovery for the extraction of calcium soaps using ethyl esters of volatile fatty acids and hexane in emulated sludge. Experimental conditions: 297 K and 250 rpm during 1 h.

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Figure 8. Scheme of valorization of primary sludge to obtain calcium soaps.

7.2 Tables

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of solvents used for the recovery of calcium soaps from sewage sludge.

Table 2. Results of lipids recovery from samples of sewage sludge using ethyl butyrate and hexane.

Solvent	Density kg/m³	Water solubility g/L
Hexane	665	0.013
Ethyl acetate	902	73.72
Ethyl propionate	884	22
Ethyl butyrate	879	6.168

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of solvents used for the recovery of calcium soaps from sewage sludge.

Entry	Solvent	% TS of Sludge	% SL of TS	Solvent/Sludge weight ratio	Recoverability (%)
1	Ethyl Butyrate	6.47	22.5	0.46	20
2		6.47	22.5	0.59	59.3
3		11.2	13.7	0.46	41.2
4		11.2	13.7	0.58	70.9
5		10	15.6	0.46	9.42
6		10	15.6	0.59	40.1
7		11.8	21.6	0.59	84.3
8		10	6.13	0.23	10
9		10	6.13	0.59	64.6
10		9.61	17	0.46	12.8
11		9.61	17	0.59	51.6
12		11.8	12.8	0.23	29.7
13		11.8	12.8	0.59	57.7
14	Hexane	4.3	23	1	87.3
15		11.3	23	1	88.3
16		8.4	23	1	93.3
17		7.8	13.7	0.25	49.3
18		7.8	13.7	0.63	63.3
19		7.8	13.7	1	78.3
20		8.4	23	1	74.1
21		8.4	23	0.6	42.3
22		8.4	23	0.23	30.4
23		9.61	17	0.59	20.4
24		7.8	13.7	0.23	18.3

TS: Total Solids

SL: Saponifiable lipids

Table 2. Results of lipids recovery from samples of sewage sludge using ethyl butyrate and hexane.